

D6.2 - Demonstrators and success stories from the use cases

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Deliverable Abstract
<p>The document showcases the demonstrators and the success stories from the 9 WP6 Use cases (UC). It describes the technical development situation at M30 and it has been presented as a handbook and guidelines for target users in specific scientific domains and beyond.</p>

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Terminology *not exhaustive*

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/ Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
CINES	Centre Informatique National de l'Enseignement Supérieur
CMCC	Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
CMIP6	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (Phase 6)
CND3D	Conservatoire National des Données 3D
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CNR-IOM	CNR - Istituto Officina dei Materiali
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
DKRZ	Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum
ECAS	ENES Climate Analytics Service
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-Pillar	Coordination and Harmonisation of National and Thematic Initiatives to Support EOSC project
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation
eTDR	European Trusted Digital Repository
F2DS	Federated FAIR Data Space
FAIR data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable data
HAL	Hyper Articles en Ligne (Open Science repository)
HPC	High Performance Computing
INFN	Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
INRIA	Institut national de recherche en informatique et automatique
INSERM	Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale
LOD	Link Open Data
NEP	NFFA Europe Project
NLP	Natural Language Processing
POC	Proof of Concept
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UC	Use Case
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VAP	Virtual Analysis Platform
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package
WG	Working Group

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Executive summary

This deliverable, D6.2 “Demonstrators and success stories from the Use cases” has been structured as a handbook and guidelines for end-users around the demonstrators delivered by the Use cases involved in the WP6 EOSC-Pillar project. The description of each demonstrator has been focused on the following points: the objective, the targeted users, a summary of their provided services and user-guidelines, and finally how the services proposed will be integrated into the EOSC, if this is already applicable.

In reason of a six-months extension for the WP6, the deadline to submit the demonstrators shifted from M24 to M30. The present version describes the version of demonstrators available at M30. Even if it is not fully complete at least for some of the demonstrators introduced, it can be considered as an intermediate version to be used for integration and testing towards Users’ communities, as it has been scheduled until the end of the project at M42. This document is a living document and it will be updated following advances of those Use cases that expressed the need to have more time for technical improvement of their demonstrators as it is described in the second amendment to the project.

An updated version will be available following ongoing progress of demonstrators’ implementation, deploying functionalities, achieving results. These elements will be addressed into the final deliverable of the WP6 EOSC-Pillar project.

1. Introduction

WP6 has been structured around nine Use cases (UC) based on the requirements of scientific communities connected to scientific production and intended to improve the usage of data in a FAIR perspective. For that purpose, activities have been focused on the implementation of functional demonstrators of the services set up in the UCs with an emphasis on their genericity and scalability. The final objective is to generalize the implementation of the applied UCs by integrating the services developed so far in the EOSC-Pillar environment and to make them accessible to other communities through the EOSC.

EOSC-Pillar selected nine different and science-related demonstrators:

- **Demonstrator #6.1 - Defining Procedures/Services to enforce Data provenance for thematic communities and beyond.**
Provenance management is a key component in order to guarantee scientific data discovery, reproducibility and results interpretation. This demonstrator takes into account needs coming from two different communities: (i) material science/nanoscience and (ii) climate science.
- **Demonstrator #6.2 - Agile FAIR Data for Environment and Earth System Communities.**
This demonstrator aims at facilitating and speeding up the access to the distributed data sources and provide a web-based processing environment for Earth Sciences communities.
- **Demonstrator #6.3 - Integration of Data repositories into EOSC based on communities' approaches.**
This demonstrator wants to provide technical tools to address preservation, re-usability and reproducibility of data repositories with a focus on Agri-food, material and health sciences domains.
- **Demonstrator #6.4 - Software Source Code Preservation, Reference and Access.**
The objective of this demonstrator is to provide a solution for the preservation of massive collections of software source code into EOSC.
- **Demonstrator #6.5 - FAIR Principles in Data Life-cycles for Humanities.**
The aim of this demonstrator is to build a bi-directional relationship between publications and data or datasets deposited in different repositories for Social Sciences and Humanities.
- **Demonstrator #6.6 - Exploring reference Data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics.**
This demonstrator aims at bridging already available Galaxy computing services and data repositories for bioinformatics communities.
- **Demonstrator #6.7 - Suitable Data formats for seismological Big Data provisioning via web services.**
The objective of this demonstrator is to develop automated tools to standardize datasets for seismological community and new implementation of the standard services capable of working with a large amount of data.
- **Demonstrator #6.8 - Virtual definition of big Datasets at seismological Data centres according to RDA recommendations.**
This demonstrator aims at making the Data Collections System, designed within the activities of RDA, generic enough and ready to be adopted by different communities within EOSC.
- **Demonstrator #6.9 - Integrating Heterogeneous Data on Cultural Heritage.**
This demonstrator aims at integrating in a cloud environment data resulting from scientific analyses and experiments on cultural heritage artefacts with other documentation.

1.1 The Template

The template used to collect information and data concerning the demonstrators has been organized around two major axes, namely, (i) the description of the current development status (at M30 of the EOSC-Pillar project), and (ii) the technical innovations set-up eventually in coordination with other parts of the project (WP5 and WP7) and therefore the identification of future possible developments and implementations in the framework of the EOSC. Indeed, the template's objective was to inscribe the demonstrators developed by the WP6 Use cases into the framework of the structuring of EOSC and therefore put in evidence the added-value provided by the EOSC-Pillar project in addressing and anticipating needs of the research communities involved and eventually more largely.

The description of the demonstrators has been structured around the following characteristics:

- **Objectives of the demonstrator:** Based on the Use-Case description available in D6.1 "State of the art and community needs", this section presents the objectives achieved throughout the implementation of activities by the Use cases accordingly with requirements and needs from the scientific communities involved in the EOSC-Pillar project.
- **Targeted users:** This property lists the targeted current and future potential users and stakeholders of the demonstrator.
- **Necessary data sources & EOSC services used:** This property defines the data necessary to run the β -version of the demonstrator, their location, the way to get access and if the data are pre-processed elsewhere. This section highlights also the services developed and provisioned by the EOSC-Pillar consortium or by other EOSC entities used in the framework of the UCs' activities to develop the demonstrator.
- **Summary of provided services:** This section is focused on the description of the services provided by the demonstrator.
- **Guidelines to use the services:** As a handbook, this section highlights the way to use the services provided. Somewhere screenshots of the user interface have been added to explain how to use the services (in the β -version), if they are already available.
- **EOSC integration:** This section describes how the services developed have been integrated in or eventually will be scaled up to the EOSC marketplace.

2. Demonstrators

2.1 Demonstrator #6.1 - Defining Procedures/Services to enforce Data provenance for thematic communities and beyond

Provenance management, that track all the processes applied to data, from the origin to the final results, is critical to enable reusability in scientific research experiments.

The Use Case 6.1 comprises 2 scientific domains: Material Science/Nanoscience and Climate Science. We describe here 3 demonstrators, respectively 1 for Material Science/Nanoscience and 2 for Climate Science domain.

In the Material Science/Nanoscience domain, the demonstrator, as detailed below, has the final goal to adapt the W3C PROV standard, to the provenance procedures so far identified in specific cases within the Istituto Officina dei Materiali (CNR-IOM) of National Research Council (CNR).

In the Climate Science domain, the W3C PROV standard has been considered as a recommended set of specifications for tracking processes and responsibilities as well as describing provenance structures within complex experiments and large workflows on scientific data.

The PROV Family of Documents defines a data model ([PROV-DM¹](#)) along with the corresponding serializations (i.e., [PROV-N](#) as a notation aimed at human consumption, [PROV-O](#) as the ontology for mapping the PROV data model to RDF, [PROV-XML](#) and [PROV-JSON](#) as XML schema and JSON representation for the PROV data model, respectively) and other supporting definitions to enable the inter-operable interchange of provenance information in heterogeneous environments such as the Web.

The *PROV data model* defines the mapping of a core set of concepts to types and relations, as shown in the table below.

PROV Concepts	PROV-DM types or relations	Name
Entity	PROV-DM Types	Entity
Activity		Activity
Agent		Agent
Generation	PROV-DM Relations	WasGeneratedBy
Usage		Used
Communication		WasInformedBy
Derivation		WasDerivedFrom
Attribution		WasAttributedTo
Association		WasAssociatedWith
Delegation		ActedOnBehalfOf

Table 1. Mapping of PROV core concepts to types and relations

An **Entity** is a physical, digital, conceptual, or other kind of thing with some fixed aspects.

An **Activity** is something that occurs over a period of time and acts upon or with entities: it may include consuming, processing, transforming, modifying, relocating, using, or generating entities.

An **Agent** is something that bears some form of responsibility for an activity taking place, for the existence of an entity, or for another agent's activity.

The three primary classes are related through a core set of relations:

¹ <http://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-dm-20130430/>

Generation: the production of a new entity is completed by an activity;

Usage: an activity starts utilizing an entity;

Communication: the exchange of some unspecified entity by two activities, one activity using some entity generated by the other;

Derivation: the transformation of an entity into another, the update of an entity resulting in a new one, or the construction of a new entity based on a pre-existing entity;

Attribution: the ascribing of an entity to an agent;

Association: the assignment of responsibility to an agent for an activity, indicating that the agent had a role in the activity;

Delegation: the assignment of authority and responsibility to an agent (by itself or by another agent) to carry out a specific activity as a delegate or representative.

A graphical view of the **PROV Core Structures** is shown in the following figure.

Figure 1: PROV Core Structures

Starting from the W3C PROV specifications, these PROV Core concepts have been applied in the form of adaptations and extensions on top of the existing scientific data services in order to enhance provenance capabilities, thus addressing FAIR-oriented full provenance management.

A. Material/Nanoscience domain

2.1.1 Objectives of the demonstrator

The main objective of this demonstrator is the definition of guidelines and recommendations on how to manage the important aspect of data provenance for the wide community behind the NFFA-Europe PILOT Project ([NEP²](https://www.nffa.eu/news/project-updates/pilot-nep/)).

² <https://www.nffa.eu/news/project-updates/pilot-nep/>
www.eosc-pillar.eu

2.1.2 Targeted users

The present targeted users come from the community of the nanoscience domain. However, we foresee an extension to the material science domain with the possibility to extend to other communities as well in the future. In a typical scenario, a nano-scientist collects and analyses data using distributed infrastructure. End users run data analytics workflows on compute facilities and produce data outputs. These data outputs are published and shared within the community. Retrieving the provenance information, allows end users to have a better understanding of data lineage as well as of the entire analytics process associated with it, providing the full history of data.

2.1.3 Necessary data sources & services used

The Nanoscience data sources come from the “Surface sStructure and Reactivity at the atomic Scale” (STRAS) research group of the CNR-IOM Institute in Trieste. The dataset has been made available by the lab owner, through the NFFA Datashare cloud platform, in order to organize it from a FAIR point of view and test the data provenance procedures on such a dataset. At present, infrastructure services used, were all internal to NEP. We are now evaluating some services from WP5, in particular the F2DS – Federated FAIR Data Space. The goal here is to see if by means to F2DS, we can integrate our service catalogue to enlarge the chances to make it findable by a wider community.

2.1.4 Summary of provided services

The services provided are related with the creation of a database to store scientific images metadata and the development of a web service to visually explore these metadata through interactive tools. The main objective was the FAIRification of a scientific archive of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM), and the creation of a curated dataset to allow researchers to build the provenance of data.

Description of services provided:

- **STM Metadata Database:** a data service to store scientific images metadata. It helps the discovery of images on the whole dataset by selecting different metadata values as filters, thus improving the findability and accessibility.
- **STM Metadata Explorer³:** an easy-to-use and interactive web service that researchers can use to interact with the STM Metadata Database and explore images metadata through interactive and downloadable plots. The crucial component of this web service is metadata enrichment with information on sample composition, obtained with machine learning techniques. It allows visualization and download functionalities directly in the web browser. This service is integrated within [Trieste Advanced Data Services \(TriDAS\)](#), designed to enable advanced data services connected to scientific data resources to help researchers in their work.

On top of these data services, during the FAIRification workflow, was applied W3C PROV standard to describe the provenance of metadata, from the original STM images to the ones curated and available on the TriDAS website.

2.1.5 Guidelines to use the services

Researchers can interact visually with the Metadata database, using the STM metadata explorer (Figure 2) on the Trieste Advance Data Services website (TriDAS).

³ https://tridas.nffa.eu/dashboard_stm/

TriDAS is ready to fly!

Trieste Advance Data Services (TriDAS) is designed to enable advanced data services connected to the already stored scientific data resources on the NEP shared storage infrastructure. The platform will host several virtual access services that can be classified in broad categories:

- 1) Data Services developed within specific experimental/computational techniques;
- 2) Data Services developed at a more general level to address specific class of scientific data (i.e. images, 3D archives).

The platform is seamlessly integrated in the NEP data repository, allowing users or proposal user groups to access the services immediately and without any need of data transfer. It will be fully operational at Month 31. Services currently offered by the infrastructure: All the participating infrastructures have been known to offer high level services and research in many initiatives of international level, including EOSSC, EUDAT, RDA, and NFPA-Europe. A short overview of currently available services, divided in simulation and data, is reported below. Additional information on current offer, research topics.

SEM EXPLORER

Explore a scanning electron microscope database with more than 100k images simply selecting the metadata you need. Plots are interactive and downloadable.

[SEM database explorer](#)

STM EXPLORER

Explore a 100K scanning tunneling microscope database simply selecting the metadata you need. Plots are interactive and downloadable.

[STM database explorer](#)

Figure 2: Trieste Advance Data Services website ([TriDAS](#))

It allows users to explore the images metadata through interactive and downloadable plots. Users interacting with the platform, can find relevant images using just the selected metadata fields without providing specific information. Based on the number of fields selected, two plots are displayed: a quantiles plot to show the distribution of the images with respect to the values of the field and a scatter plot that shows the number of images for each combination of the two fields.

Figure 3: The web service workflow on the TriDAS website

In both plots, hovering on top of plot objects creates a pop-up showing information about that object: the number of images and value intervals for quantiles plots and the number of images and metadata value for each field in the scatter plot. The right toolbar lets users interact with the plots by moving, zooming in and out, and saving plots as images. These features are useful for a first exploration of the

dataset which then should be downloaded for further analysis and image visualization. To address this issue, the scatter plot allows the selection of a specific metadata combination to retrieve a new page containing a table with metadata fields for each image's in that subset. On this page, researchers can select, order, filter, and search images based on their metadata values. Moreover, the ID column consists of each image unique identifier in the database and, by clicking on it, the corresponding STM image is rendered and shown in a new page, where a download feature is included to obtain data, metadata, plot and provenance metadata for each image. The [source code](#), as well as a list of all used software package are publicly available and annotated in the provenance metadata.

To describe the provenance metadata of STM images, we used the W3C PROV standard. The different components concerning the workflow of the principal events performed during the FAIRification process of STM images, from the Raw data generated by Omicron Variable Temperature STM (VT-STM) measurements to the final image, were mapped with the W3C PROV core concepts. For the mapping, were considered three components of PROV-DM: entities and activities, derivations, and agents with their responsibilities as shown in the table below.

W3C PROV concepts		STM elements
PROV types	Entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw data Reference dataset Structured & FAIR dataset Filtered image
	Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VT-STM measurements Image selection & retrieval Image labelling process Metadata selection
	Agents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> STRAS research group Data scientist Research user VT-STM microscope Analysis software
PROV relations	Usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Image selection & retrieval used Raw data Image labelling process used the Reference dataset Metadata selection used the Structured & FAIR dataset
	Derivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reference dataset derived from Raw data Structured and FAIR dataset derived from the Reference dataset Filtered image derived from Structured & FAIR dataset
	Generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw data was generated by VT-STM measurements Reference dataset was generated by Image selection & retrieval Structured & FAIR dataset was generated by Image labelling process Filtered image was generated by Metadata selection
	Attribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw data was attributed to STRAS research group Reference dataset was attributed to STRAS research group and Data scientist Structured & FAIR dataset was attributed to STRAS research group and Data scientist Filtered image was attributed to Research user
	Association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VT-STM measurements were associated with STRAS research group and VT-STM microscope Image selection & retrieval was associated with Data scientist Image labelling process was associated with STRAS research group and Data scientist Metadata selection was associated with Research user
	Delegation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VT-STM microscope acted on behalf of STRAS research group Analysis software acted on behalf of Data scientist

Table 2. Mapping between the elements of STM case study with W3C PROV concept types and relations. The roadmap of the FAIRification activities and the subsequent mapping with W3C components leads to the provenance workflow presented in Figure 4. Then, a practical implementation of the workflow

presented in Figure 4 was conducted by using a PROV Python Library for W3C Provenance Data Model. The provenance document created in Python was then exported in a JSON representation for PROV, PROV-JSON, thus providing a compact and accurate representation of PROV that is particularly suitable for interchanging PROV documents, allowing reproducibility and interoperability.

Figure 4: Graphical representation of the provenance workflow of STM images based on PROV-DM structures.

PROV Activities are represented as lilac rectangles, PROV Agents as light orange pentagons and PROV Entities in light yellow ovals. The responsibility properties are depicted in pink, while the properties used to construct provenance chains among Activities and Entities in black. The workflow starts with **VT-STM measurements** attributed to **STRAS research group** and associated with both **STRAS research group** and **VT-STM microscope** that acts on behalf of **STRAS research group**. **VT-STM measurements** generated **Raw data** that were used during **Image selection & retrieval** to generate the **Reference dataset**. The **Reference dataset**, which was derived from **Raw data**, was attributed both to **STRAS research group** and **Data scientist**. **Analysis software** acts on behalf of **Data scientist** and **Research user**. **Image labelling process**, associated with **Data scientist** and **STRAS research group**, used the **Reference dataset** to generate the **Structured & FAIR dataset**. Therefore, **Structured & FAIR dataset** derived from **Reference dataset**. At last, **Metadata selection** associated with **Research user** used the **Structured & FAIR dataset** to generate a **Filtered image** that was attributed to the **Research user**.

The dataset containing 7287 STM images, together with their provenance description and all [source code](#) used, was published on Zenodo⁴. Furthermore, a paper that describes all the work performed so far was submitted.

⁴ Tommaso Rodani, Elda Osmenaj, Alberto Cazzaniga, Mirco Panighel, Cristina Africh, & Stefano Cozzini. (2021). Dataset of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM) images of graphene on nickel (1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5808724>

2.1.6 EOSC integration

Now, the demonstrator is built as a stand-alone instance within the TriDAS website. The services are ready as proof of concept and it is not yet clear how they will be scaled up to the EOSC portfolio. We are currently integrating our data provenance procedures and ideas developed so far with the W3C PROV standard and only then we will move toward EOSC integration.

B. Climate science domain

The two climate demonstrators described below address provenance tracking at two different levels:

- the first one (first-level) refers to the whole end-to-end scientific workflow including a proper reference to input and output datasets via PIDs;
- the second one (second-level) provides a focus on some first-level tasks, like those ones regarding data analytics which can be represented themselves as a workflow of micro-tasks (analytics operators) which may usually be in the order of hundreds or thousands.

The main idea is to navigate the first level provenance to have a complete understanding of the overall high-level end-to-end workflow and then have the opportunity to drill-down into some specific analytics tasks to get more detailed information about their internal workflow in terms of micro-tasks or analytics operators. In such a context we can refer to two-level workflows, as two-level provenance management accordingly.

2.1.7 Climate Science Demonstrator #1: Objective of the demonstrator

The objective of the demonstrator is to provide guidance and kick start tools to scientists for the generation of W3C PROV conformant provenance descriptions as part of their scientific climate data analysis notebooks. The main focus of this demonstrator is to provide a concrete starting point to integrate the EOSC-Pillar use cases in 6.1, 6.2 and 6.8, by integrating the aspects of provenance generation with PIDs and PID collections (as part of provenance records) and Jupyter notebooks e.g. hosted on the D4Science VRE. Climate scientists need simple templates and rules they can follow to ease the provisioning of PROV records in addition to generated analysis results which they want to share or which should be used in downstream community use cases (e.g. by the climate impact research community).

The approach will demonstrate:

- The generation and integration of PIDs in provenance records (thus demonstrating the integration with the EOSC/EUDAT B2Handle service based on the pyhandle client).
- The application of the PIDCollection concept (it is unclear whether integration with the new PID Collection service can be achieved as part of this demonstrator)
- The usage and integration of helper tools to generate provenance records as part of jupyter notebooks.

The approach is applied to the scientific use case developed as part of the Task 6.2 use cases (Agile FAIR data for environmental sciences) which are accessible as part of the ECAS service and are also accessible via the D4Science virtual research environment.

2.1.8 Targeted users

The service targets two different user groups: on one hand the climate modelling community developing science notebooks underlying e.g. scientific publications, which want to share their data analysis approaches and data products; on the other hand downstream communities (e.g. the climate impact community) using these notebooks, and data analysis results as starting points for their research activities, thus requiring detailed provenance information for those artefacts.

2.1.9 Necessary data sources & services used

The first version of this use case will use data hosted at cloud storage and climate data centers. The processing can be done on D4Science VRE hosted JupyterHub service as well as climate data centers (e.g. the ECAS instances hosted at DKRZ and CMCC).

2.1.10 Summary of provided services

This demonstrator does not provide a stand-alone service but a set of simple to use templates and tools which can be used in the context of climate science notebooks to enable researchers to provide standards conforming provenance descriptions for their data products. The tools also try to bridge related use cases (PID collections in WP 6.8).

Guidelines to the services. Guidelines are provided in the form of documentation and interactive Jupyter notebooks currently hosted on Gitlab demonstrating the general approach based on concrete data analysis examples (which were developed as part of the WP 6.2 use case). Currently the GiLab repository (https://gitlab.dkrz.de/data-infrastructure-services/climate_data_provenance/-/blob/master/notebooks/use_case_provenance.ipynb) features a notebook for the generation of provenance records of the global temperature mean calculation. The user can analyse and visualize data of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project CMIP6, by choosing one variable of multiple experiments and compare the results of different models. In particular, the user will analyse the historical experiment in combination with one of the shared socioeconomic pathway (SSP) experiments. In the end and additionally to the scientific results, provenance records will be created in the form of a provenance graph.

2.1.11 EOSC integration

The use case is integrated into with the D4Science VRE as well as the ECAS service that are part of the EOSC catalogue. Data infrastructure integration based on iRods is planned, yet the level of integration which can be achieved until the end of the EOSC pillar is unclear. The same is true with respect to the automatic integration of metadata in the EOSC-Pillar metadata service providers. Several parallel routes are currently being explored (OAI harvesting to the EOSC D4Science data catalogue, integration into the Federated FAIR Data Space etc.)

2.1.12 Climate Science Demonstrator #2: Objectives of the demonstrator

Climate research makes use of lots of data coming from the modelling and observational climate communities. In this domain, provenance management plays a key role both for numerical end-to-end simulations at data center level and in the inner data analytics workflows. In addition, due to data exploration complexity, provenance management is key to ensuring scientific data reproducibility and sharing, along with results interpretation and data history tracking.

This demonstrator aims to contribute to the design of a provenance workflow in the field of climate science by identifying suitable provenance procedures as well as leveraging the use of the W3C PROV standard. To account for in-depth provenance support within the climate processing services, a second-level provenance management complying with the W3C PROV standard has been elaborated, thus addressing FAIR principles at a finer granularity.

2.1.13 Targeted users

The climate demonstrator is mainly aimed at scientific users from the core climate modelling community, who are interested in performing scientific data analysis workflows with a stronger provenance support (so called second-level) able to track analytics activity at the level of single operators. In a typical scenario, end users run data analytics workflows on a compute facility and produce data outputs (e.g. final products, intermediate results) which are published and shared within

the community. End users search for some data and retrieve provenance information for a better knowledge of the data lineage and of the entire analytics process associated with it. The proposed approach could be further generalized to be applied to other domains sharing similar objectives and needs.

2.1.14 Necessary data sources & services used

The climate use cases are built on top of the ENES Climate Analytics Service ([ECAS](#)), which is the server-side compute infrastructure exploited in [UC6.2](#). ECAS is one of the [EOSC-Hub](#) Thematic Services and also a Compute Service in the [IS-ENES3](#) project, that enables scientific end-users to perform data analysis experiments on large volumes of multidimensional data by exploiting a PID-enabled, server-side, and parallel approach. It consists of two main instances hosted at [CMCC](#) and [DKRZ](#).

ECAS provides access to a set of specific CMIP⁵ variable-centric collections. These datasets, mainly related to CMIP5 and CMIP6 data products, are downloaded and kept in sync with the ESGF⁶ data archive. In this regard, an integration with the [F2DS](#) (Federated FAIR Data Space) system developed in the context of WP5 activities is being carried out by joining the current efforts from UC6.2. Specifically, the metadata of the datasets exploited in the demonstrator could flow through the F2DS Metadata repository in order to be harvested by the F2DS Metadata catalogue service.

2.1.15 Summary of provided services

Some existing ECAS modules have been enhanced with various adaptations and extensions to fully address FAIR-oriented provenance management. In particular, based on information about the executed analytics operators that are tracked by the Ophidia⁷ *analytics engine*, scientific users can run their analytics workflows and get fine-grained (second-level) provenance information, represented according to the W3C PROV specifications. More in detail, a Python application was developed allowing users to retrieve the provenance documents related to a specific analytics workflow in several formats, such as XML, JSON, RDF or graphical format. This application exploits the [PROV](#) Python library - an implementation of the W3C PROV Data Model supporting PROV-O (RDF), PROV-XML, PROV-JSON import/export - to map the ECAS concepts into the proper W3C PROV concepts. The following table shows provenance mapping between W3C PROV and the ECAS workflow elements.

W3C PROV	ECAS objects
Entities	Climate data in NetCDF format (input) Results file(s) in NetCDF format (output) Ophidia datacube
Activities	Ophidia analytics tasks, also known as operators (import, export, subsetting, data reduction, timeseries analytics, etc.)
Generation	NetCDF file or datacube generated by an Ophidia operator
Usage	NetCDF file or datacube used by an Ophidia operator as input
Derivation	Datacube derived from a NetCDF file (by the <i>import</i> operator) or from another datacube (by some other Ophidia operator) NetCDF file derived from a datacube (<i>export</i> operator)

Table 3. Mapping between W3C PROV and ECAS concepts

⁵ CMIP (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project), <https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip>. A collaborative framework designed to improve knowledge of climate change.

⁶ ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation), a federated data infrastructure for the management, dissemination and analysis of model output and observational data.

⁷ Ophidia, <https://ophidia.cmcc.it>. A CMCC Foundation research project addressing big data challenges for eScience.

The entities in an ECAS analytics workflow are the input climate data and the results files (output), both in NetCDF format, as well as each datacube⁸ generated/used internally by an Ophidia operator. The activities can be mapped to the tasks within the analytics workflow, each one related to a specific Ophidia operator.

Entities and activities are connected through a *generation, usage or derivation* relation.

Figure 5: Graphical representation of the ECAS core concepts based on PROV-DM structures

In addition, the application relies on a graph database platform (based on [Neo4J](#)) to store ECAS objects and their relationships and properties according to the core classes and properties provided as a basis by the PROV Ontology. In this case, the graph nodes are mapped to entities (*datacube* and *file* labels) and activities (*task* label), while the types of relationships connecting entities and activities are set to *used*, *wasGeneratedBy* or *wasDerivedFrom*. In this way it is possible to handle and query PROV graphs, thus retrieving the data lineage of an object through Cypher queries supported by Neo4J, including the entire analytics workflow associated with the object. This aspect is particularly noteworthy for addressing strong re-use of data as well as reproducibility.

2.1.16 Guidelines to use the services

ECAS integrates both data and analysis tools to support data scientists in their daily research activities through [ECASLab](#), the scientific data analytics environment built on top of ECAS. It consists of several components like a compute cluster, a JupyterHub instance with a large set of pre-installed Python libraries for running data manipulation, analysis, and visualization, and a variable-centric CMIP data archive synchronized with the ESGF catalog.

⁸ S. Fiore, A. D’Anca, C. Palazzo, I. T. Foster, D. N. Williams, G. Aloisio, “Ophidia: Toward Big Data Analytics for eScience”, ICCS 2013, June 5-7, 2013 Barcelona, Spain, ICCS, volume 18 of Procedia Computer Science, page 2376-2385. Elsevier, 2013

Figure 6: ECASLab data analytics environment - user workspace

The ECAS instance hosted at CMCC provides support for fast computations through the **Ophidia data analytics framework**⁹, which enables data-intensive analysis exploiting advanced parallel computing techniques and smart data distribution methods. In some scientific use cases, the management of processing chains or workflows with tens or hundreds of analytics operators can be a real challenge. Ophidia is able to handle complex data analytics workflows of operators through the definition of a JSON representation compliant to a request schema¹⁰ for the workflow DAG (Directed Acyclic Graph) specification and the support of different constructs, such as dependencies, massive, iterative and parallel tasks, flow and error control. Analysis experiments can be designed according to this schema and can easily be shared with other users (e.g. through GitHub), fostering experiment reuse. In such a scenario, users can then write an analytics workflow in the form of a JSON file and submit it to the workflow manager by a single command through the [Ophidia terminal](#), i.e. the client application provided with the Ophidia analytics framework.

Figure 7: Ophidia workflow and Terminal

⁹ S. Fiore, D. Elia, C. Palazzo, F. Antonio, A. D'Anca, I. Foster, G. Aloisio, "Towards High Performance Data Analytics for Climate Change", ISC High Performance 2019, LNCS Springer, 2019

¹⁰ https://ophidia.cmcc.it/documentation/users/appendix/json_request.html

Then, based on information about the executed tasks that is tracked by the Ophidia server, users can retrieve the corresponding provenance documents in XML, JSON, RDF or graphical format by executing the Python application developed in the task.

The **multi-model Precipitation Trend Analysis (PTA)** has been selected as a pilot case. It has been implemented as an ECAS analytics workflow and executed on 17 climate models from the CMIP5 experiments for a total of about 300 tasks.

Figure 8: Definition of the multi-model Precipitation Trend Analysis workflow

The analysis consists of two main steps:

- the first part includes a number of identical sub-workflows, each associated with a specific climate model involved in the CMIP experiment and independent of the others. Each sub-workflow evaluates the precipitation trend for both the historical and future scenario (e.g. RCP¹¹, SSP¹²) datasets and performs a trends comparison over the considered domain.
- the second part is the final stage to perform a multi-model statistical analysis on the output of each previous sub-workflow.

The following two figures show the fine-grained provenance information compliant with the PROV standard related to (a) one of the sub-workflows in the first part of the experiment and (b) the final phase, respectively.

¹¹ RCP (Representative Concentration Pathway), a greenhouse gas concentration trajectory adopted by the IPCC. Four pathways were used for climate modelling and research for the IPCC fifth Assessment Report (AR5) in 2014.

¹² SSP (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways), scenarios of projected socioeconomic global changes up to 2100 used to derive greenhouse gas emissions scenarios with different climate policies.

Figure 9a: Fine-grained provenance information related to one of the sub-workflows in the first phase of the PTA experiment

Figure 9b: Fine-grained provenance information related to the final phase of the PTA experiment

To provide a simple and understandable view of the complex provenance description generated by the demonstrator, the following picture shows the provenance information tracked for one of the tasks in the PTA analytics workflow, e.g. a task related to the import of a NetCDF file into the Ophidia datacube space.

Figure 10: Fine-grained provenance information captured at the second level of the PTA workflow based on W3C PROV specifications

2.1.17 EOSC integration

The demonstrator is built on top of the ENES Climate Analytics Service, which is one of the thematic services included in the EOSC-hub service portfolio. However, at the moment, it is just meant as a proof of concept, so it is not included as a feature of the ECAS resource onboarded on the EOSC Portal Catalogue & Marketplace. Additional developments are required in this regard and will be further investigated in the future. Yet, an integration with the [EOSC-Pillar 4 Earth Science VRE](#) deployed on the EOSC-Pillar D4Science facilities in the context of the "Demonstrator #6.2 - Agile FAIR Data for Environment and Earth System Communities" is being carried out, thus strengthening the links with UC6.2 and WP7.

2.2 Demonstrator #6.2 - Agile FAIR Data for Environment and Earth System Communities

2.2.1 Objective of the demonstrator

Earth environment sciences & Geosciences require a large panel and volume of data from satellite, in-situ observations and climate models, that are managed and preserved separately in domain-dependant repositories of national or European infrastructures. As the data sources are widely distributed, it induces real difficulties to achieve inter-processing and integrated uses of the data for comprehensive studies at domain or cross-domain level.

In this context, the goal is to offer services that facilitate and speed up the access to the distributed data sources and provide a web-based processing environment for Data Science notebooks supporting the [Pangeo](https://pangeo.io/) community platform (<https://pangeo.io/>). This use case aims also to enhance data discovery and data access, relying on existing services provided by the Earth Sciences communities such as in France, the Research Infrastructure Data Terra (<https://www.data-terra.org/en/accueil/>), and in Europe, the consortium of Environment Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) (<https://envri.eu/>), the climate community, etc. [More information in this video](#)

The Data Science notebooks will enable cross-domain data processing, regardless of scientific themes or organisations. Indeed, it will allow to perform, for example:

- Cross-sources studies such as integration of satellite and in-situ observation;
- Multi or cross-disciplinary studies in “Earth Environment sciences” communities (Solid Earth / Atmosphere / Ocean / Continental surfaces such as volcanoes and earthquakes, river flow or sustainability and safety of the coastline, Climate, etc.)
- Cross-disciplinary studies with other communities, such as biosphere (carbon cycle, impact of changes on biodiversity, etc.) or human activities (soil artificialisation, etc.)

2.2.2 Targeted users

The web-based processing environment proposed by the demonstrator have to address the needs of two types of user of Data Science notebooks on Earth environment & Geosciences data:

- Scientists, who want to run ready-to-use data processing “Pangeo ecosystem-based” scripts on their temporal and geographical areas of interest;
- Data analysts, who want to develop, test and run their own data processing “Pangeo ecosystem-based” scripts adapted to their needs.

2.2.3 Necessary data sources & services used

The data sources from UC6.2 partners, RIs and Data Centers used in the Use Case are listed below:

Ifremer/ CNRS for DATA TERRA RI	Argo dataset is a collection of 3000 in-situ data floats for temperature and salinity in the first 2000 m of the water column. Access on IFREMER HPC data storage or	CORA CMEMS dataset built from a collection of in-situ data, either profiles or time series. This gridded ¹³ product provides values for temperature and salinity between	SMOS gridded data issued by the eponym satellite on ocean surface salinity from 2010 to 2019. CATDS is responsible for data processing and	GSLH dataset is a collection of gridded multi-mission sea surface heights computed with respect to a twenty-year mean. Several variables are proposed (Sea
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¹³ This is a term used to describe how data is represented spatially in geographic information system. “Gridded data means data sets ranging from simple, uniformly spaced grid points along a single dimension to multidimensional grids containing several different types of grid values”.

	from <u>catalogue</u>	1990 and 2018. Access on IFREMER HPC data storage or from <u>catalogue</u>	provides access on IFREMER HPC storage or from <u>catalogue</u>	Level Anomaly, Absolute Dynamic Topography, Geostrophic Velocities). Access on CNES HPC data storage (xarray-zarr format) or from <u>catalogue</u>
DKRZ	CMIP6 climate model data (~3 PByte), <u>local intake catalogue</u> (Optional data sources :ERA 5 data - > 1PByte), Grand Ensemble data set, ..)	CMIP5 climate model data (~1.5 PByte, online as well as offline tape data) <u>Harvesting, catalog etc.</u>	CORDEX regional model data (~ 400 TByte) (https://cordex.org/)	
CMCC	CMCC models contribution to CMIP5 (https://esgf-node.cmcc.it/thredds) and CMIP6 (https://esgf-node2.cmcc.it/thredds)	ESGF specific data collections (https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/search/cmip5-dkrz , https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/search/cmip6-dkrz)		

The demonstrator was initially built on top of the IT services and resources proposed by national infrastructures involved in the project. These include HPC facilities and cloud computing resources from UC 2 partners as listed below.

Ifremer/ CNRS for DATA TERRA RI	1.DATARMOR hosted by Ifremer is an HPC platform equipped with 11088 CPUs and 50+ TB of memory. In addition to computational capabilities, it also provides high performance, parallel storages such as GPFS and Lustre (https://hpc.netl.doe.gov/docs/lustre/introduction/index.html) which provide respectively 5PB and 3PB. A scheduler acts as an interface between users and hardware and provides ability to run Jupyter notebooks.		
DKRZ	2.WDCC World data center of climate, closely connected to the IS-ENES / ESGF. International Federation of data nodes serving climate model data. IS-ENES constitutes European contribution to ESGF and adds FAIR data services provided by WDCC. <u>WDCC catalog</u> -- some datasets are also	3.DKRZ HPC and data center. Dedicated German HPC resource for climate community. Holds large model data pool associated to compute resources. Non-national access possible via IS-ENES Transnational Access service activity. Jupyter-hub service available to run scripts directly	4.Copernicus data store provider and IS-ENES/ ESGF data nodes for climate model data. Additionally, compute service provider via WPS interface. (Activity together with European centers IPSL in France and STFC/CEDA in UK)

	integrated in EOSC b2find catalog	accessing the data pool	
CMCC	5.ECAS Cluster. Dedicated compute facility (100 cores) + JupyterHub-based VRE (including libs for data manipulation, analysis and visualization) available prior registration.	6.CMCC SuperComputing Centre. National facility dedicated to climate change research study. It holds large model data pool associated with a data science environment for scientific data analysis.	7.IS-ENES/ESGF data nodes hosted at CMCC for CMIP5 and CMIP6 CMCC contribution

Starting from UC6.2 partners experience and joining efforts from both Environmental and Geosciences communities, the demonstrator has evolved to provide a Virtual Data Analysis Platform (VAP), thus enabling on-demand data browsing, processing and visualization. In this regard, the demonstrator exploits data services and compute facilities provided by the EOSC Pillar WP5-data layer and WP7-Infrastructure layer, respectively.

Here are the key resources from the other WPs used in this demonstrator.

HPC and cloud computing resources from WP7 partners:

- D4Science (<https://www.d4science.org/>) Virtual Research Environment and computing resources to run Data Science Notebooks; a second scenario is expected to use CINES Virtual Research Environment and computing resources
- iRODS (<https://irods.org/>) services from UC6.2 and WP7 partners, to ease and fasten data access from the web-based processing environment by synchronizing data from the distributed data repositories to the computing resources;
- Software Heritage (<https://www.softwareheritage.org/>) solution from UC6.4, for the archive and sustainability of the source code of UC6.2 Data Science notebooks;
- Connection to WP5 data layer services to demonstrate the cross-domain metadata catalogue enabling data discovery. The first scenario connects to D4Science and further scenarios are expected to connect to the Federated FAIR Data Space.

Figure 11: Technical implementation plan for the POC

2.2.4 Summary of provided services

The use-case's partners have deployed a Virtual Data Analysis Platform on EOSC-Pillar D4Science facilities: [EOSC-Pillar 4 Earth Science VRE](#). With this service, the user is able to conduct cross-domain or cross-sources analysis on remote platform and HPC, without downloading the data or running the analysis on his local computer.

The EOSC-Pillar4Earth Science VRE provides the user with a personal Jupyter Lab workspace, from where he can access PANGEO tools (libraries, Python Notebooks, etc.) and Data Science Notebooks developed by the UC's partners. The user can either develop his own Jupyter Notebook, or adapt a ready-to-use Jupyter Notebook to his needs, and run the Notebook on-demand on datasets of interest (provided by the EOSC-Pillar UC6.2 partners) on remote facilities (D4Science HPC).

Figure 12: Data Science Notebook running on EOSC-Pillar 4 Earth Science VRE

The sub-services provided through this implementation are described below:

	Status at M30 – December 2021
1. Data Science Notebooks , to offer a web-based processing environment for scientists and data analysts within the ecosystem of Pangeo	Several data processing scripts developed and fully tested by the partners of Use Case 6.2. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See their description & links to demonstration videos below
2. Data services , to speed up and facilitate access to data of repositories from several domains	Different applications tested by UC6.2 partners: iRODS for Data Terra, Swift for DKRZ, local download for CMCC. On-going developments to access CMCC data through Swift
3. Discovery services , to provide a cross-domain catalogue	Discovery of data collections used by the use-case’s partners through D4Science catalogue, test of data FAIRification through F2DS metadata repository and catalogue. On-going improvements of GEO-DCAT mapping and display in F2DS.

2.2.4.1 - Data Science Notebooks

All Jupyter notebooks available in the D4Science EOSC-Pillar 4Earth Science VRE demonstrate the use of PANGEO tools to conduct on-demand online analysis on different types of data.

DATA TERRA Earth Observation Data Science Notebooks:

- **argo_gslh_colocation_sea_level**: With this notebook, the user learns how to exploit PANGEO tools to cross-analyze Sea Level Anomalies satellite data and pressure anomalies in situ data on his area of interest.

To do so, from Jupyter notebook use **Argo** dataset, a) select geographical area of the dataset using **dask** (<https://dask.org/>) and **parquet** (<https://parquet.apache.org/>), visualize the sub-dataset, b) select ARGO float (<https://argo.ucsd.edu/how-do-floats-work/float-types/>) by

platform number and compute Sea Level Anomalies interpolation on Argo float positions and GSLH data, visualize the result. See the [Demonstration video](#) of this notebook.

- **cora_smos_colocation_salinity**: With this notebook, the user learns how to exploit PANGEO tools to combine sea salinity parameter from different data sources (satellite data and in situ data) on his time and area of interest directly online and visualize the result. To do so, here are the different steps showed in the Notebook: from jupyter/notebook use **CORA** dataset, a) select geographical area of the dataset using **dask** and **zarr** (<https://zarr.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>), visualize the sub-dataset. b) select the same **SMOS** area, compare the two areas after spatio-temporal average to collocate the two datasets, compute the difference between the two selected areas for salinity parameters, visualize the result.
- **gslh_analysis**: With this Jupyter Notebook, the user will use gridded sea-surface altimetry data (**GSLH**) to explore list of variables, coordinates and metadata, visually examine some of the data, compute mean sea level using **dask**.

DKRZ Climate Data Science Notebooks:

- **temperature_threshold_analysis**: With this notebook, the user learns how to exploit PANGEO tools to a) search and use historical experiment or one of Shared Socioeconomic Pathway experiment from CMIP6 climate models without downloading the data, b) count the annual summer days for his year and area of interest and c) visualize the results online. To do so, here are the different steps showed in the Notebook: Use intake catalog to search and access data (Jupyter notebook) + Xarray (<https://docs.xarray.dev/en/stable/>) based processing (for all data sources) (*options to consider later on: data transfer to include external observational data sets, PID assignment to processing results =joint use case with 6.1*). For more details, the user can consult the [Demonstration video](#) of this notebook.
- **temperature_anomaly_analysis**: With this notebook, the user learns how to exploit PANGEO tools to compare historical and SSPs experiment (Shared Socioeconomic Pathway) from different CMIP6 (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project) climate models, analyze the data without downloading it, and obtain the global mean temperature anomaly on a chosen time range. To do so, here are the different steps showed in the Notebook: Mean calculation across large ensemble of climate simulation data - processing based on combination of Xarray and CDO (climate data operator toolbox) - for CMIP6 data, climate indices calculations, climate diagnostics calculations

CMCC Climate Data Science Notebooks:

- **pr_Rnnmm_index**: With this notebook, the user learns how to exploit PANGEO tools to a) search and use the precipitation variable among CMIP6 models and experiments without downloading the data, b) obtain the annual count of days when precipitation exceeds a given threshold on his year and area of interest and c) visualize the result online. To do so, here are the different steps showed in the Notebook: From Jupyter Notebook use a) **intake** catalog to search and discover CMIP6 data, b) **xarray** and **Dask** to compute in parallel the *annual count of days when precipitation exceeds a given threshold*, c) **Cartopy** (<https://scitools.org.uk/cartopy/docs/v0.15/index.html>) and **Matplotlib** (<https://matplotlib.org/>) to plot the results. For more details, the user can consult the [Demonstration video](#) of this notebook.
- **mean_temperature_and_ETR**: With this notebook, the user learns how to exploit PANGEO tools to a) search and use any variable among CMIP6 models and experiments without

downloading the data, b) calculate, for example, the air temperature average or the extreme air temperature range on his time range of interest and c) visualize the result online.

To do so, here are the different steps showed in the Notebook: From Jupyter Notebook use a) **intake** catalog to search and discover CMIP6 data, b) **xarray** and **Dask** to compute in parallel the *temporal average* over a multi-file dataset and the *Extreme Temperature Range* climate index, c) **Cartopy** and **Matplotlib** to plot the results. For more details, the user can consult the [Demonstration video](#) of this notebook.

- **PyOphidia_analysis**: This notebook shows how to exploit the [ECAS service](#) at CMCC and, in particular, the [Ophidia framework](#) and its Python bindings, PyOphidia, to implement and run some simple examples of climate data analysis exploiting a parallel, server-side approach. To do so, the steps are as follow: From Jupyter Notebook use the [PyOphidia](#) library to run parallel, server-side data analytics tasks on the ECAS compute facilities hosted at CMCC by exploiting the **Ophidia HPDA framework**.

2.2.4.2 - Data services

Fast and efficient access to large, heterogeneous and distributed data is one of the challenges the Use case had to tackle. In order to avoid copying data to the VRE, which requires time and storage resources, the data access methods were improved, providing a single data access point which is either Swift (DKRZ) or iRODS (DataTerra).

Swift is an OpenStack Object Store project, which allows the storage and retrieval of large datasets with a simple API. More information on the use of this software can be found on the DKRZ User Portal (<https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/swift>). Based on this software the DKRZ developed the Python package *TZIS* (<https://gitlab.dkrz.de/data-infrastructure-services/tzis>), which enables the user to convert climate model data from NetCDF into the cloud-optimized Zarr format and write them into the DKRZ institutional Swift Object Storage. From there the data can be easily accessed by any resource such as the D4Science VRE.

iRODS (Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System) enables easy management and seamless access to data distributed on different locations and supports (<https://irods.org/>). Data Terra datasets are read directly through UC6.2 iRODS server, already converted in analysis-ready formats such as Zarr and Parquet. Some improvements regarding the iRODS server configuration and clients development will be performed.

Together with *Intake* (a Pangeo Python package that interfaces the user with requested data without requesting their location: <https://github.com/intake/intake>), these services provide the user with fast and optimised data access and processing through D4Science 4EarthScience VRE.

2.2.4.3 - Discovery services

The description of ocean and climate data collections (listed in 2.2.3 - *Necessary data sources*) were integrated in [D4Science Eosc-Pillar Data Catalogue](#), allowing the discovery of datasets from different domains and infrastructures through a single entry point. However, harvesting protocols and methods were not optimal for all infrastructures.

In order to improve the FAIRness and granularity precision of these data collections, which are described using different metadata models and ontologies depending on the discipline, the F2DS service is currently tested.

The F2DS service architecture allows to collect, map and publish the metadata of heterogeneous and distributed data sources in a common and standard metadata model using the DCAT 2 model and its extensions such as [GEO-DCAT AP](#), which allows a more thorough description of spatial and temporal information.

Figure 13: GEO-DCAT mapping through F2DS Metadata repository

The mapping to GEO-DCAT AP metadata model can be done manually or automatically for datasets described in ISO 19115 metadata model through the use of the F2DS User Interfaces and services. Mappings will be made available to other users to serve as examples.

The metadata will be enriched with terms described in discipline-specific machine-actionable semantic artefacts using the dedicated service of F2DS in link with EOSC Pillar T5.5, once available. The FAIRified datasets will be published in the Fair Data Point ¹⁴ and harvested by the D4Science data catalogue.

To improve the content and granularity of climate data descriptions, and therefore enhance their discovery through D4Science catalogue, DKRZ is currently testing the implementation of [STAC](#) (Spatio Temporal Asset Catalogue), with the aim to test its connection to F2DS and D4Science catalogue.

2.2.5 Guidelines to use the services

Access EOSC-PILLAR Earth Science VRE on D4Science

1. Open the following URL in the web browser of your choice: <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillar4earthscience>
2. If you don't have an account on D4Science, please create one and confirm your account using the link you'll receive by e-mail;
3. Find, among all services proposed on the page, the one called "EOSC-PILLAR Earth Science VRE". Click on "Request Access" and "Confirm request" to send your request to D4Science VRE moderators. The services you have requested access to are identified by a light orange label "waiting for approval".

¹⁴ <https://www.fairdatapoint.org/>

D6.2 - Demonstrators and success stories from the use cases

- Once a D4Science VRE moderator has approved your request, you will receive a confirmation e-mail containing a link to connect to the VRE you have selected, and be able to access the VRE services.

Figure 14: Access EOSC-PILLAR Earth Science VRE on D4Science

You can also access the D4Science4EarthScience VRE from the EOSC-Pillar Gateway page (<https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eosc-pillar-gateway>), in the right-side box “My Working Environment” or “Use-case Environments”.

The D4Science VRE for Earth Science is a virtual working environment from where you can browse a catalogue containing the datasets used in UC 2, import algorithms or access a JupyterLab environment.

Figure 15: Access EOSC-PILLAR Earth Science VRE through EOSC-Pillar Gateway page

Access your JupyterLab environment and UC6.2 Jupyter Notebooks

Once connected on D4Science EOSC-Pillar 4 Earth Science VRE, click on “Jupyter” under “Analytics” in the upside bar menu, to open your Jupyter Lab workspace and choose your server options (we recommend the largest option).

Figure 16: Access your JupyterLab environment on D4Science EOSC-Pillar4EarthScience VRE

Then click on the workspace folder in the leftside bar, and follow this pass: “VREFolders/EOSCPillar4EarthScience/notebooks”.

All Jupyter Notebooks available on the D4science EOSC-Pillar4Earth Sciences VRE are listed in the left-side bar. You will find all Data Science Notebooks developed by the Use case partners that are part of UC6.2 demonstrator under the following folders: CMCC, DKRZ, DataTerra.

Figure 17: Access UC6.2 Jupyter Notebooks

Run a Jupyter Notebook from D4Science Eosc-pillar 4 Earth Science VRE

From your Jupyter Lab environment, you have access to the workspace folder which is a public folder containing all notebooks produced by UC6.2 and shared with all users of the Earth Science VRE. We therefore recommend, before taking any action, to create a personal folder in the root folder (/home) in which you'll be able to copy any notebook of your choice and modify it, update it or simply run the notebook without any interferences.

Figure 18: Launch UC6.2 Jupyter Notebook from personal workspace

Once you have copied the notebook of your choice in your personal folder, simply click on the Notebook to launch it and run each cell after another by clicking on the “Play” button. Each cell is numbered, if you see a star symbol instead of a number between squared brackets [*], it means the cell is still processing, you need to wait for the action to be completed before running the next cell.

Figure 19: Run UC6.2 Jupyter Notebook

2.2.6 EOSC integration

The Use case was designed as a proof-of-concept, to demonstrate what EOSC could offer to Earth environment and geosciences communities. Further developments and improvements would be required to scale up the demonstrator to operational level and integrate it in EOSC services.

2.3 Demonstrator #6.3 - Integration of Data repositories into EOSC based on communities' approaches

2.3.1 Objectives of the demonstrator

The main goal of Use case 6.3 demonstrator is to explore the current limitations and provide concrete recommendations and tools to address preservation, re-usability and reproducibility of data repositories.

This will be achieved using an on-development Material Sciences model repository, as well as existing Agri-food and Health sciences Dataverse¹⁵ and iRODS¹⁶ implementations, two data and metadata repository software used for storage, management and publication. However, the developed tools and connectors will be discipline or community agnostic as highlighted by three different communities involved in the demonstrator, and will enrich the whole EOSC services ecosystem.

2.3.2 Targeted users

The demonstrator aims to address the needs of the AgriFood community based on scientific user stories¹⁷, notably the phenotyping community represented by PHENOME-EMPHASIS¹⁸ researchers. However, as the task deliverables are generic interoperability connectors, the potential users also include all Dataverse based repository users, and EOSC marketplace users for the Data In the cloud deliverables.

2.3.3 Necessary data sources & services used

The β -version relies on data from two existing services.

- Data INRAE¹⁹ : generic data and metadata repository of INRAE. The data itself consists of files from the various researchers' communities of the institute;
- PHIS²⁰ : ontology-based repository for plants phenotype data gathered in real time by sensors used by the PHENOME-EMPHASIS community.

The data from these two services can be accessed:

- for Data INRAE with a public unauthenticated access to the published datasets, via the repository user interface or via REST APIs²¹,
- for PHIS data, an API is available but requiring authentication. The data from PHIS used will also be accessible through Data INRAE.

In addition to these two data sources, the demonstrator also relies on the following services are:

- **The D4Science infrastructure**²² provided CNR-ISTI.
- **FAIR Federated Data Space (F2DS)**²³ provided by task 5.1 of WP5.
- **PICO2** service provided by INRIA and INRAE.
- **Cloud computing resources and services** provided by INRAE and France Grilles.
- **The VITAM archiving platform**²⁴ (CINES) instance, an eTDR²⁵ service provided by CINES.

¹⁵ <https://dataverse.org>

¹⁶ <https://irods.org>

¹⁷ <https://repository.eosc-pillar.eu/index.php/s/fWNGnbzmpcY5ZJ3>

¹⁸ https://www.phenome-emphasis.fr/phenome_eng/

¹⁹ <https://data.inrae.fr>

²⁰ <http://www.phis.inra.fr>

²¹ <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/5.3/api>

²² <https://ckan-eoscpillar.d4science.org/organization/eoscpillar4agrifood>

²³ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillarresdatactlg/f2ds-repository>

²⁴ <https://github.com/ProgrammeVitam/vitam>

- **B2SAFE²⁶ storage** (iRODS) node from CINES as part of eTDR.
- **The Marketplace²⁷** service provided by Fraunhofer Institute for Mechanics of Materials.

2.3.4 Summary of provided services

Building on these resources, task 6.3 aims to provide the following services, as summarized in the video <https://repository.eosc-pillar.eu/index.php/s/6xqjQipjJ2DH3Tq>:

1. A connector module to archive data from Dataverse repositories to CINES VITAM and EOSC/EUDAT B2SAFE via eTDR services.

Figure 20: Connector module from Dataverse

2. Set-up computing platforms such as JupyterHub, Renku, Binder and Rshiny in order to compute data from Dataverse based repositories or raw data.
3. A connector module accessible from Dataverse repositories and EOSC Marketplace to exchange data with reproducibility platforms (JupyterHub, Binder, Renku and Rshiny).

Figure 21: Connector module to reproducibility platforms

²⁵ (in French) <https://www.cines.fr/europe/eudat-cdi/service-etdr/>

²⁶ <https://www.eudat.eu/b2safe>

²⁷ <https://www.the-marketplace-project.eu/en/AbouttheMarketplaceProject.html>

4. A connector module between Dataverse repositories and Fraunhofer Marketplace to allow use of its tools on external data.

Figure 22: Connector module from Dataverse to the Marketplace

5. Integrate Dataverse and D4Science VRE

2.3.5 Guidelines to use the services

2.3.5.1 Connector module to archive from Dataverse repositories to CINES VITAM and EOSC/EUDAT B2SAFE services.

The proof of concept of this service is in development. We are developing an application that will read the data to archive from INRAE data repository and generate the corresponding archiving «SIP» packages containing the files and metadata. These files will be deposited in shared folder using the VITAM tool provided by CINES. VITAM will consume these files to finalize the archiving process.

Figure 23: Connector module to CINES VITAM and EOSC/EUDAT B2SAFE services

2.3.5.2 Connector module to exchange data with computing platforms (JupyterHub, Binder, Renku and Rshiny).

As this feature is currently only accessible on developers' environment, access to the test instance will be documented later on. In Dataverse, access the dataset you want to use. This dataset must contains files (Full documentation on searching datasets or files and on general use of Dataverse software can be found here : <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/>).

Figure 24: INRAE Dataverse

To use a single file, click on its download icon on the dataset page. You may also use “Access File” if on the file’s page. A dropdown list will appear. In the section “Explore Options” select the “JupyterHub” option.

Figure 25: INRAE Dataverse “access” to file/dataset

You will be redirected to an interface to configure your computing environment. Adjust the parameters to your needs. You will then be redirected to the reproducibility platform. The dataset or file selected www.eosc-pillar.eu

can be accessed through different methods depending on the platform. At this time, only the connection to jupyterHub can be documented:

- JupyterHub:

Figure 26: JupyterHub

The datafile will then appear on the environment:

Figure 27: JupyterHub environment

And you will be able to explore it by clicking it or using it in a script. For full JupyterHub documentation see <https://jupyter.org/documentation>.

If you want to make computation on all the files of a dataset, you don't need to send them one by one to Jupyterhub. Instead, in Dataverse, access the dataset you want to use and then:

- click on the "Access Dataset";
- a dropdown list will appear. In the section "Explore Options" select the "JupyterHub" option;
- you will be redirected to the jupyterhub as described above for the file;
- the next steps are the same as described above for a file.

Figure 28: Jupyter Hub environment “access” to file/dataset

2.3.5.3 Connector module between Dataverse repositories and Fraunhofer Marketplace. The proof of concept of this service has not been developed yet (see EOSC integration).

2.3.5.4 Integrate Dataverse and D4Science VRE

As this feature is currently only accessible on developers’ environments, access to the test instance will be documented later on. In Dataverse, access the dataset you want to use. This dataset must contain .tab format files (Full documentation on searching datasets or files and on general use of Dataverse software can be found here: <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/>).

Figure 29: Integration to D4S

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For the .tab file you want to use, click on the “Access Dataset”, if you are at the dataset level or “Access File”, if you are at the file level. A dropdown list will appear. In the section “Explore Options” select the “D4Science” option.

Figure 30: D4S environment “access” to file/dataset

Depending on the dataset’s terms of use you may have to accept the Terms

Figure 31: D4S terms of use

You will be redirected to the D4Science Virtual Research Environment <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eosc-pillar-gateway/workspace> where you will have to log in:

Figure 32: D4S login interface

The file will then appear in your files on your workspace under the DOI of the source dataset you selected:

Figure 33: D4S workspace

2.3.6 EOSC integration

As per the evolution of Data INRAE repository into a national research data repository: Recherche Data Gouv²⁸, this service will be made accessible on the EOSC Marketplace, along with the connectors when ready for production use.

In addition, the source code of the different demonstrator applications is made publicly available²⁹ and reusable, so that other instances of the services may be deployed in the EOSC environment.

²⁸ (in French) <https://projet-recherchedatagv.ouvri.lascience.fr/le-projet/a-propos-de-recherche-data-gouv>

²⁹ <https://forgemia.inra.fr/dipso/eosc-pillar>

2.4 Demonstrator #6.4 - Software Source Code Preservation, Reference and Access

2.4.1 Objectives of the demonstrator

Leveraging the experience of [Software Heritage](#), this task will design and pilot a solution for the preservation of massive collections of software source code (billions of files with links to publications) into EOSC.

More specifically, we aim to:

- develop a deposit API for research software archival;
- develop an access API for retrieval of archived software;
- standardize a persistent identifier schema (PID) for referencing billions of archived software artefacts;
- integrate the above APIs and Services with [EOSC eTDR](#);
- develop a pilot to fully host the software archive onto existing EOSC infrastructure.

With these goals in mind, the demonstrator for the UC6.4 will show how these API and services can be used by EOSC partners to ensure long term preservation and persistent identification of any software source code used in research experiments to help reproducibility.

Long term preservation of the Software Heritage Archive is guaranteed by the Software Heritage project itself (via the mirror network), but as part of this UC, a second resiliency layer will be provided by keeping an archived version of the Software Heritage Archive into the CINES archiving platform [Vitam](#). This cold storage backup is not meant to be used as a usable/searchable copy of the main Software Heritage Archive, but as a disaster recovery backup to ensure long term preservation.

2.4.2 Targeted users

The demonstrator targets any scientific community that make use of software in their research activity (that is any scientific community nowadays).

At individual level:

- a researcher can ensure a software source code involved in the production of a paper is archived by Software Heritage, and
- he/she is able to precisely and intrinsically identify any piece of source code using SWHID,
- she/he is able to retrieve any piece of code from the Software Heritage Archive from the SWHID, even if the original data source for this code (original git repository, forge, etc.) is not available any more.

At community/institution level:

- an institution can deposit source code software it produces, with a curated process and with metadata, directly into the Software Heritage Archive, the way HAL currently allows its users to deposit software in HAL and have this software automatically pushed in the Software Heritage Archive, and get resulting SWHID for identification and citation purpose. This integration level requires a signed agreement with the Software Heritage project.

2.4.3 Necessary data sources & services used

- Most of the services described in this UC are currently running at production level.
- The main web application is located at <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/>
- The public API is located at <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/api/1/>
- The Vitam archiving platform provided by CINES will be used to store the backup copy of the Software Heritage Archive.
- Authorization and Authentication Infrastructure provided by EOSC partners can be integrated with Software Heritage AAI as Identity Providers.

2.4.4 Summary of provided services

- **Searching** the Software Heritage Archive for a source code by its name or origin URL: this service is available as a web application on <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/browse/search/> and as a public API on <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/api/1/origin/search/doc/>. This service is publicly available. The public API is rate-limited for unauthenticated users.
- **Browsing** the Software Heritage Archive is possible using the web app on <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/>. Navigating the underlying Software Heritage graph structure is available via the public API on <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/api/1/>. This service is publicly available. The public API is rate-limited for unauthenticated users.
- Ask the Software Heritage Archive to take a snapshot of a publicly available source code repository (git, mercurial or subversion) is available as the **Save Code Now** service on <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/save/>. This service is publicly available.
- **Deposit** an archive file (zip, tar) containing source code and a codemeta metadata description of the deposited source code is available at <https://deposit.softwareheritage.org/>. This service is only available as an API (based on SWORD) but a command line interface tool is provided to help using this API. This service is only available to some authenticated users.
- **Retrieve** archived software source code is possible navigating the Software Heritage Archive and using the Vault service at <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/browse/vault/>. This Vault service is responsible for gathering all the files and content from the Software Heritage Archive and build a zip file ready for the user to download. It is possible to download a single file, a complete directory (as a zip file) or a full git history. This service is publicly available.
- **SWHID** (persistent and intrinsic identifier) of any source code artefact stored in the Software Heritage Archive can be retrieved while navigating the archive. The web application allows to craft either Core SWHID (identifier of the artefact only, without qualifiers) or Extended SWHID (with qualifiers, like the Origin the artefact comes from, or a fragment qualifier to identify only a portion of a source code file, e.g. a specific function or class). Computing locally the SWHID of a source code artefact is possible either using custom code implementing the [SWHID public specifications](#), or using the [command line interface tool](#) provided by Software Heritage.

2.4.5 Guidelines to use the services

- Search & navigate

Figure 34: Example of results for the query "nakala"; returns a list of projects which name (actually project URL) involves the "nakala" word.

Figure 35: Browsing page for a project archived by Software Heritage; here, the dfih-tools project from the Huma-Num gitlab repository. The main navigation page for a project shows the content (list of files and directories) of the project (for the latest gathered revision) as well as the content of the README file, if any. The user can browse the directory tree for

the selected branch, can browse the git history, download the displayed directory (as a zip file), or get the SWHID for the displayed object.

- **Get a SWHID**

Figure 36 : Every displayed object, when browsing the Software Heritage Archive, has a permanent and unique identifier, the SWHID, that can be displayed via the "Permalink" tool.

- **Download a copy of the code**

Figure 37 : When the displayed object is a Directory or a Revision, it's possible to download it using the "Download" tool button. Internally, the service responsible for gathering all the software artefacts and create a zip file ready to download is the Vault.

2.4.6 EOSC integration

- The Software Heritage Archive has been integrated as part of the [EOSC service catalog](#).
- The authentication service of the Software Heritage Archive has been linked with Indigo-IAM Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) as part of the WP7 effort to help EOSC partners interested in integrating Software Heritage services in their platform.
- Some partners of the EOSC-Pillar project have expressed their interest in integrating the Software heritage Archive in their platform (especially UC 6.2 and possibly 6.5), but this has not been done yet.

2.5 Demonstrator #6.5 - FAIR Principles in Data Life-cycle for Humanities

2.5.1 Objectives of the demonstrator

The aim of the demonstrator is to build a bi-directional relationship between publications deposited in HAL, the French national archive for publications and data or datasets deposited in NAKALA, the French research data repository for SSH data, and to expose the relationships thus created so that they can be easily found and exploited, particularly at European level to promote and increase the sharing of scientific knowledge. Thus, a second objective will be to test tools for displaying and disseminating these links, so that they can be exploited in the European web of data. A more detailed description of the demonstrator can be found in the [MS26](#) of the EOSC PILLAR project.

2.5.2 Targeted users

The demonstrator targets the SSH community, as NAKALA is the French research repository for SSH communities, and HAL is a multidisciplinary repository with a specific portal for SSH communities. But the principles of the prototype are generic enough to be extended to another communities.

2.5.3 Necessary data sources & services used

The demonstrator uses data from HAL (<https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/>) and from Nakala (<https://nakala.fr/>). We use APIs available in each of the repositories to get them.

2.5.4 Summary of provided services

From a publication in HAL, searching and browsing datasets in Nakala (Nakala search API):

- Create the link between the publication and the dataset via its identifier in Nakala.
- Using a standard vocabulary (Datacite) to type the relationship.
- Send the link to Nakala with the HAL publication identifier.

The service is only available to some authenticated users, and publication's owners.

Figure 38: HAL and Nakala connectors

Display the relationship on the landing page of the publication in HAL:

- display citation;
- visualize data in the landing page of the publication in HAL;
- link with the landing page of data in Nakala.

Finally, the way the relationships will be exposed is detailed in 2.5.6 (Cf. Schema)

2.5.5 Guidelines to use the services

User interface is available at HAL-preprod website (<https://hal.halpreprod.archives-ouvertes.fr/related/resources>).

- Create a relationship for a publication in HAL:

Figure 39: HAL interface

- Search in Nakala (and browse) and add a relationship:

Figure 40: Search interface in Nakala repository

- Landing page of the publication in HAL:
 - citation of data
 - visualization (preview)

Figure 41: Visualization in HAL

2.5.6 EOSC integration

At the moment, the demonstrator is built as a standalone instance within HAL-preprod website (<https://hal.halpreprod.archives-ouvertes.fr/related/resources>) and Huma-Num has the same approach. The service is ready as a proof of concept but we foresee an additional effort in order to disseminate these relationships, by exposing it in different ways, make it searchable and exportable in various standardized formats and make it harvestable by OAI-PMH.

Another option is to use a server (Mercure) where the relationship will be published and from where repositories could “listen” and take the relationships of interest. Publishing and listening on the Mercure server is done after authorization from the server administrator (for now Huma-Num). See the schema below:

Figure 42: Mercure relation Hub schema

2.6 Demonstrator #6.6 - Exploring reference Data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics

2.6.1 Objectives of the demonstrator

Galaxy³⁰ is one of the prevailing workflow management systems for bioinformatics, aiming to make computational biology accessible to research scientists that do not have computer programming or systems administration experience. How can scientists connect this powerful tool seamlessly with many data sources? How can they do so in a coherent way using different instances of Galaxy? Can they run it locally or on a secured infrastructure that handles patient data? Can they compare the results of those different scenarios? Those are the main questions this Use case wants to address.

The aim of this Use case will be to design the possible interactions between already available Galaxy computing services and data repositories, in order to build an integrated and interoperable service for ELIXIR and the wider Life Science user community as a whole.

Building on top of existing French and Italian national services, the Use case will produce guidelines and best practices, and implement a service prototype based on different scientific scenarios in order to:

1. Allow access to reference data from different Galaxy deployments for data analysis.
2. Facilitate the deployment of Galaxy instances close to the data.
3. Provide coherency between different existing Galaxy deployments.
4. Ensure health data security requirements are met throughout the process.

Four user-based scenarios were designed to achieve these objectives and represent concrete application of this Use case.

Scenario 1: Public Galaxy instance(s)

A user needs to implement a Galaxy workflow that requires input data from institutional repositories (Inserm repository, INRAE repository) or data from a public database. This can be done using a Galaxy public server, in our prototype hosted on an EOSC-Pillar partner infrastructure (INFN), and using the EOSC Pillar Federated FAIR data space for searching and accessing required input data. Finally, output data are moved to an institutional repo/storage.

Scenario 2: Close-to-the-data deployment

A user needs to perform analysis on big files (and/or many files) through an I/O intensive workflow, but he doesn't want to or it is not possible to upload data on a public Galaxy instance. He/she obtains from the federated dataspace needed information about data location and nearest infrastructures. He can easily deploy a private Galaxy instance, through Laniakea³¹, on an infrastructure close to the data. This Galaxy instance has the same features than the central one, therefore the same workflow can be used. Output data are stored locally and referenced in an institutional repository.

Scenario 3: Health data with restricted access

Users need to perform analysis on a dataset with strong legal requirements (personal/health data). As a result, this dataset can only be accessed from a secured bubble, and there are strong restrictions and procedures for deploying Galaxy in such an environment. They get this information, along with details about access request procedure, from the federated dataspace. Once they can access the data, they can perform the analysis on a private Galaxy instance, deployed using Laniakea in secured environment. Output data are stored in the perimeter of these secured environment and, if possible, is populated elsewhere and referenced in an institutional repository.

Scenario 4: Reproducibility and verification

User needs to compare workflows and/results obtained through scenarios 1, 2 and 3. For that, he needs to be sure that analyses have been produced through the same workflow, and if there are any

³⁰ <https://usegalaxy.org/>

³¹ <https://laniakea.readthedocs.io>

difference, be able to identify them. Similarly, he/she should be able to reproduce results from those scenarios.

The schema below describes the architecture of the theoretical scenarios:

Figure 43: Theoretical scenarios

2.6.2 Targeted users

The demonstrator targets the Bioinformatics community, and especially that of the ELIXIR ESFRI. Implemented scenarios build up on the concrete technical needs from the research community working on hCNV (human Copy Number Variation), but the prototype is generic enough to be extended far beyond this specific use.

The processes and good practices resulting from the implementation of the demonstrator can, in turn, extend beyond the Bioinformatics community and serve as basis for bringing any other platform, tool or workflow management system to the EOSC level.

2.6.3 Necessary data sources & services used

The demonstrator bridges various data repositories to Galaxy through EOSC-Pillar WP5's Federated FAIR Data Space. Used repositories and data sources are:

- **Inserm prototype data repository**
(<https://dataverse-test.ovvirlascience.fr/dataverse/inserm>):

Structured as part of the French national plan for a health data hub, this service is designed with three objectives in mind: Storing data, describing/identifying/referencing them, and making them available.

- **Public data hosted by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST):**

Copy number variation (CNV) is a type of genomic structural variation that contains segmental duplications or deletions of a DNA fragment. The human Copy Number Variation community (hCNV) aims to implement processes to make the detection, annotation and interpretation of these variations easier. Several methods are used to explore these variations such as the Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology that enabled precise detection of small CNVs. The results of the sequencing, called "reads" are hosted by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST):

https://github.com/genome-in-a-bottle/giab_data_indexes

- In its first version, the demonstrator uses training data for somatic variant calling, available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2582555>, through a lighter Galaxy workflow
- **Used Galaxy service** is provided by T7.4 "Ready-to-use" **Laniakea@ReCAS service**:

It is already available and provides bioinformatics analysis tools to the Elixir Italian and European community. The Laniakea@ReCaS service allows end users to easily deploy Galaxy private instances.

Galaxy is a simple yet powerful web-based workflow manager, where it is easy to import, manage, perform analysis on users' datasets and then share results and workflows. This improves reproducibility and contributes in offloading researchers of many menial tasks, allowing them to better focus on interpreting any evidence harnessed from data. Furthermore, of particular importance is the possibility to quite easily import into the workflow manager a wealth of external data that are already available on public repositories. Laniakea provides the possibility to deploy different instance configurations, in terms of CPUs, RAM and storage. Finally, provides easy access and management of reference data is available with systems in place to avoid any unnecessary redundancy. In fact, a CVMFS³² based storage ensures that all the Galaxy instances supported by the Laniakea service share access to a rich common set of reference data that can however be expanded by users of single instances if needed. The INDIGO PaaS layer³³, which is the core middleware of Laniakea, recently made available the possibility to deploy and configure Virtual Machines (VM) on private networks. This means that the VMs are completely isolated from the external world and can be reached only through a properly configured VPN/bastion. The reference setup for the VPN server is based on OpenVPN and a PAM (Pluggable Authentication Modules) module has been developed in order to extend the authentication and authorization mechanism using the INDIGO IAM³⁴ service. Finally, Laniakea allows the creation and the management of encrypted storage associated with these instances, thus improving the isolation and safety of these virtual environments. An overview of how the service can be used, as well as how the interface looks like, is presented in the following video demo:

<https://youtu.be/WZey8XrCp1I>

2.6.4 Summary of provided services

Service1: Public Galaxy instance(s)

The demonstrator service is a public Galaxy server. The implemented workflow is described here (up to the variant calling step). It has been selected to properly test the prototype, since it is not requiring a huge amount of resources (32GB RAM and 16 CPUs), but still data output can be used to validate our prototype. Moreover, since this workflow is commonly used to analyse human genetic data, currently under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), it can be used to properly test the third scenario.

³² <https://cernvm.cern.ch/fs/>

³³ <https://www.indigo-datacloud.eu/paas-orchestrator>

³⁴ <https://www.indigo-datacloud.eu/identity-and-access-management>

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Figure 44: Workflow for service 1

Figure 45: Workflow for service 1 Zoom on first steps

Galaxy specification:

- **Galaxy release 20.05**
- **CPUs 16**
- **RAM 32GB**
- **Storage 500GB**
- **Tools:** specific tools for variant detection installed (manually)
- **Workflows:** variant detection workflow

Deployment information:

The EOSC-Pillar T6.6 public server was deployed using the Laniakea development instance, which exploits the official Galaxy project Ansible³⁵ roles to install and configure the service.

The Pillar instance has been also configured to have a straight forward access to reference data mounting the official Galaxy CVMFS repository, using the Galaxy official Ansible role (<https://galaxy.ansible.com/galaxyproject/cvmfs>)

Service 2: Close-to-the-data deployment

This service uses a specific deployment of Laniakea (Laniakea@ReCAS, jointly provided by INFN-Bari and CNR-IBIOM).

Galaxy specification:

- **Galaxy release:** 20.05
- **CPUs** 16
- **RAM** 32GB
- **Storage** 500GB
- **Tools:** specific tools for variant detection installed
- **Workflows:** variant detection workflow

Deployment information:

Automatic deployment of «pillar-flavored» VM on the cloud infrastructure using the new Laniakea Ansible role version for automatic installation of tools and workflows (Ansible role: <https://github.com/Laniakea-elixir-it/ansible-role-laniakea-tools>,

Pillar flavour: <https://github.com/Laniakea-elixir-it/Galaxy-flavours/tree/master/galaxy-pillar>)

A full working demo of the Laniakea software used as part of the UC6.6 is available online on https://youtu.be/SK9C_MWz6Yk

Service3: Health data with restricted access

On this service user can perform the analysis using an easily deployable Galaxy instance in a secured environment. The dataset can only be accessed from a secured bubble with strong legal and ethics requirements on the storage and handling of health data. The legal and ethical requirements are needed in order to comply with the legal framework and to remove obstacles to data sharing and interoperability, according to the FAIR and Open Science principles. The research activities take into account the differences between the French Legal Order and the Italian Legal Order on this topic, in the transnational context.

A document describing the Health Data legal requirements, realised in close collaboration with task T4.1, was done and it is available on: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334878>

2.6.5 Guidelines to use the services

The whole documentation about how to use Laniakea is provided online:

<https://laniakea.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

- *Guidelines to use service 1 (public instance):*

The Galaxy public server is available at: <http://cloud-90-147-75-210.cloud.ba.infn.it>.

Access is granted after the registration.

³⁵ <https://docs.ansible.com/ansible/latest/index.html>

Figure 46: Screenshots for registration and access to the workflow

Tools are available on the left, while the « somatic variant detection » workflow is available through the menu « Shared Data -> Workflows ».

- Guidelines to use service 2 and 3:

The access to Laniakea@ReCaS is offered on a per-project basis through an [open-ended](#) call defining terms and conditions. Each project proposal is evaluated by a scientific committee and a technical board. Access to the development version of Laniakea, including the last development done in the context of EOSC Pillar project, will be granted only for testing purposes.

Figure 47: Screenshots to access to Laniakea@ReCaS

End-users interact with Laniakea through a web front-end that allows easily a general setup of a Galaxy instance. Each Galaxy instance is customizable in terms of virtual CPUs, RAM and storage through the web dashboard, and deployable with different sets of pre-installed tools.

2.6.6 EOSC integration

The Galaxy part of the demonstrator is already scaled up, as Laniakea has reached the necessary maturity level. Moreover, the integration with the Federated FAIR data space is under development.

Access to the Laniakea@ReCaS service can be requested from this [page](#)

Laniakea@ReCaS is a European Open Science Cloud provider, and the service is opened to all EOSC users through the [EOSC Marketplace](#).

For more details on UC6.6:

- UC6.6 description: <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/use-cases/exploring-referencedata-through-existing-computing-services-bioinformatics-community>
- UC6.6 poster: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5764786>
- Poster on Laniakea development: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6206807>

2.7 Demonstrator #6.7 - Suitable Data formats for seismological Big Data provisioning via web services

2.7.1 Objectives of the demonstrator

Seismology is one of the scientific disciplines with a long tradition of data sharing, standardization, and the adoption of many of the FAIR principles even since its conception. With an International Federation (FDSN) providing guidelines and formal specifications for data formats and provisioning services, in order to foster the standardization of data search, selection and retrieval, the community was able to develop an interoperable ecosystem of software clients and users.

The last decades have been characterised by a large amount of new additional permanent and temporary conventional seismic stations becoming available. It is also already clear that there are some game-changing technologies under development. The demand for new dense observations using new technologies is advancing fast. This includes what is known as Large N deployments (arrays with a huge number of easy-to-install seismic sensors), and fibre-optic based technologies (DAS), that are each starting to show their great potential in providing quality data with a wide spectrum of applications ranging from Tsunami early warning to Infrastructure monitoring.

Fibre-optic can be used to measure ground motion using the so called distributed acoustic sensing technique (DAS) (Jousset, P., 2019. Science) with existing underground fibre-optic cables (present everywhere in cities and even in the seafloor, Figure 48) up to tens of kilometres long, or even deploying dedicated short fibre-optic cables. Another alternative for the usage of fibre-optic communication cables is to deploy conventional sensors along their repeaters (typically 50-100 km intervals). These techniques allow to image the internal structure of geological faults with an unprecedented resolution, to infer creeping processes of faults at sub-micrometre step, or to provide a global network of real-time data for ocean climate and sea level monitoring.

Figure 48: Fibre optic cable on the seafloor (Jousset, P., 2019. Science, 366, 6469, 1076-1077)

Although data quality and resolution of the techniques mentioned above are different, they have in common the potential to produce large volumes of data in a very short period of time due to both the extremely dense spatial and temporal resolutions. The datasets generated by these new technologies (e.g. DAS) would make impossible to still use the same standard data formats and standard specifications for data provisioning services.

Seismological web services have been designed some years ago with particular types of user and data in mind, which are not exclusively what we see today, and these new acquisition techniques are a challenge for data centres and users (see Figure 49).

Our main aim in this Task was to keep FAIRness in the community by developing automated tools to standardize these datasets, and new implementation of the standard services capable of working with these new data. We compiled in a short video³⁶ a summary of the challenges and work done in this Task.

Figure 49: Evolution of the data archived yearly at each data center (green, yellow, and blue curves). The error bars on the right show the expected size range of a single dataset for a large-N (blue) and a DAS (red) experiment. One can see that a single large dataset could be equivalent in size to a whole year of the typical datasets currently being archived.

2.7.2 Targeted users

All seismological data centres, researchers generating seismic waveforms from fibre optic cables (DAS), seismologists studying crustal structures needing much higher resolution as previously available, or applying big data and machine-learning techniques to local/regional studies.

2.7.3 Necessary data sources & services used

Any dataset generated by a DAS unit from Silixa³⁷, one of the most important manufacturers of this type of technology, can be used as input. As this effort was published and started being used in the scientific community, another manufacturer (Alcatel) contacted us to provide support for their instruments (OptoDAS).

³⁶ <https://youtu.be/57kkGkw8-mA>

³⁷ <https://silixa.com/technology/idas/>

As the data volume is quite large, we are in contact with WP7 to investigate the chance to use services like GridFTP³⁸, or other cloud solutions to stage the data.

2.7.4 Summary of provided services

Development and publication of *dastools*, a software package designed to standardize datasets from DAS experiments. The package provides a library to access and manage proprietary formats from the manufacturers supported (e.g. TDMS, OptoDAS HDF5) datasets generated by DAS systems. This consists of Python classes which are the core of the tools provided. These classes can be imported by the users in their own code and include in it all the flexibility of *dastools*.

With these Python classes or with the command line tools provided in the package, the user will have:

1. Capability to convert to standard formats.
2. Ready-to-use standard data provisioning web services on top of non-standard data format. This is a light weight service providing data in standard formats (e.g. miniSEED) and through standard protocols (FDSN-Dataselect).³⁹
3. Provision of ready-to-use containers to use the software.

The package providing this service has been published in Quinteros, J. (2021)⁴⁰.

2.7.5 Guidelines to use the services

The package can be installed either from its repository⁴¹, or from Pypi under the name “*dastools*”.

Once installed, the utility called *dasconv* can be used to convert a DAS dataset to a standard format. In addition to that, as the DAS data is acquired at a high sampling rate, the conversion can optionally include a decimation (reduction of the sampling rate) of the data to reduce its size. The result is feasible to be archived and opened to users as any other standard seismological dataset.

Data acquired from experiments with DAS systems are usually stored in one folder. Files within this folder have names indicating the experiment and the start time of the waveforms saved. An example of the files generated in a test experiment is shown below.

```
$ ls -l
total 1577352
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:40 default.UTC_20190508_093935.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:40 default.UTC_20190508_094005.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:41 default.UTC_20190508_094035.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:41 default.UTC_20190508_094105.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:42 default.UTC_20190508_094135.409.tdms
```

There, ‘default’ is the name of the experiment and the rest is the start time with the following format:

```
experiment_TZ_YYYYMMDD_HHmms.ff.tdms
```

We include here some examples about how to use *dasconv*. A detailed explanation on how to use this tool and the others belonging to the package can be found in the documentation available in the repository.

To export waveforms from channels 800, 802 and 804 starting at 2019-05-08T09:37:35.409000 until 2019-05-08T09:38:05.400000, in miniSEED format after being downsampled by a factor of 5 (e.g. from 1000Hz to 200Hz).

³⁹ <https://www.fdsn.org/webservices/fdsnws-dataselect-1.1.pdf>

⁴⁰ Quinteros, J. (2021): *dastools* - Tools to work with data generated by DAS systems. V. 0.5. GFZ Data Services. <https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.2.4.2021.001>

⁴¹ <https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/javier/dastools>

```
dasconv -d /home/user/test/ --start "2019-05-08T09:37:35.409000" --end "2019-05-08T09:38:05.400000" default --chstart 800 --chstop 805 --chstep 2
```

To export waveforms from channels 0 and 1 from the beginning of the measurements until 2019-05-08T09:32:15, in miniSEED format after being decimated by a factor of 5 (e.g. from 1000Hz to 200Hz).

```
dasconv -d /home/user/test/ --endtime "2019-05-08T09:32:15" default --chstart 0 --chstop 1
```

To export waveforms from channels 0 to 4 from the beginning of the measurements until 2019-05-08T09:32:15, in miniSEED format after being decimated by a factor of 5 (e.g. from 1000Hz to 200Hz).

```
dasconv -d /home/user/test/ --endtime "2019-05-08T09:32:15" default --chstart 0 --chstop 4 --decimate 5
```

2.7.6 EOSC integration

This service is being delivered in a ready-to-use container in order to be adopted by as many data centres and users as possible without any limitation of the resources needed. The plan is that the data generated from the software should be able to be staged in many of the available EOSC services, like cloud solutions and federated data spaces for users to work with. For data centres, it is the perfect tool to ensure that the new dataset types will have the same FAIRness level than the standard ones. In cases of huge raw datasets, it is possible to downsample it in space and/or time to make them available through the current standard formats and service specifications.

2.8 Demonstrator #6.8 - Virtual definition of big Datasets at seismological according to RDA recommendations

2.8.1 Objectives of the demonstrator

The management of digital objects remains an area of interest that crosses disciplines, institutions and infrastructures. In this context, the need for building aggregations or collections of such objects has become an essential element. Research data management practices require not only to describe collections, but to make them actionable by automated processes to be able to cope with ever increasing amounts and volumes of data.

For many data centres, curators and dataset creators, it is difficult to assemble collections if there is the need to instantiate them, by replicating all their contents in one place. Sometimes because of storage limitations, or because some parts of the dataset appear in many collections.

But the main limitation with existing solutions for the management of data collections is that they focus on describing collections and their semantics with metadata, but do not offer a full set of generic, machine-actionable CRUD operations on them.

A Working Group from RDA prepared specifications for a Research Data Collection system to overcome these issues⁴².

This Use case aims at making the Data Collections System, designed within the activities of RDA, generic enough and ready to be adopted by different communities within EOSC.

The design of the RDA Data Collection system aims at:

- Provide CRUD operations (create, read, update, delete) for aggregations or data collections of different data objects as an essential element in the research data management practices;
- Describe the research data collections in a standardized way to make them actionable by automated processes in order to be able to cope with the increasing amounts and volumes of data.

The underlying data model of the Data Collection API can be defined by three sub-models:

Service: defines the basic functionality provided by an instance of a Data Collection System. Depending on the implementation of the system (or its configuration), some optional features could be present or not. An instance can host (locally or virtually) an arbitrary number of collections.

Collection: properties of a specific collection at the current instance. A collection can have an arbitrary number of members, including (sub-) collections.

Member: properties of a specific member of a collection.

Figure 50: Data model of collections API. S: Service. C: Collection. M: Member.

⁴² <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00022>

2.8.2 Targeted users

Libraries, or any research unit willing to provide a service which allows users to manage research data collections. This can be completely independent from the scientific discipline, the data type, and the location of the data.

2.8.3 Necessary data sources & services used

Access to a Handle/ePIC server is in the Wishlist, but it is not mandatory for the service to be used.

2.8.4 Summary of provided services

This task provides the implementation of a generic, multi-disciplinary Data Collections System based on the experience and requirements of 13 communities within the RDA Working Group. The service provided is being deployed at GFZ and could be accessed by any community.

The package includes:

- The service implementation,
- Client tools to allow users to easily build the collections,
- Container definition for communities who would like to run them on their own,
- Graphical tools to browse the service and its contents are being developed (still in beta),
- Interoperability with other services from EOSC-pillar providing information and definition of datasets (e.g. F2DS), as well as with well-known cloud storage solutions within EOSC (e.g. Nextcloud/B2DROP).

2.8.5 Guidelines to use the services

The different methods of the API available in this implementation can be seen in the following figures for each of the sub-models or levels of this API.

Service

GET /features Gets the service-level features.

Screenshot of the Swagger UI view of the features operation.

Collections

GET /collections Get a list of all collections

POST /collections Create a new collection.

GET /collections/{id} Get the properties of a specific collection.

PUT /collections/{id} Update the properties of a Collection Object

DELETE /collections/{id} Delete a collection

GET /collections/{id}/capabilities Get the capabilities of this collection

Screenshot of the Swagger UI view of the collections operations.

The screenshot shows a Swagger UI interface for the 'Members' endpoint. It lists seven API operations with their respective HTTP methods, URLs, and descriptions:

- GET** `/collections/{id}/members` Get the members in a collection
- POST** `/collections/{id}/members` Add a new member item to this collection
- GET** `/collections/{id}/members/{mid}` Get the properties of a member item in a collection
- PUT** `/collections/{id}/members/{mid}` Update the properties of a collection member item.
- DELETE** `/collections/{id}/members/{mid}` Remove a collection member item.
- GET** `/collections/{id}/members/{mid}/properties/{property}` Get a named property of a member item in a collection
- PUT** `/collections/{id}/members/{mid}/properties/{property}` Update a named property of a member item in a collection

Screenshot of the Swagger UI view of the collection members operations

A complete description about the (generic) Data Collection Service and its formal specification can be found in Weigel, T., et al (2017)⁴³

Some utilities and clients are also available in the package. For instance, *gentoken* is a utility for the service operator to create a token for users who need to get authenticated at this service.

```
% gentoken -h
usage: gentoken [-h] [-o OUTPUT] [-d DIR] [-m MAIL] [-n CN] [-e {1d,2d,1w,2w,1m}] [-V] [-v]

optional arguments:
  -h, --help            show this help message and exit
  -o OUTPUT, --output OUTPUT
                        Output file where to store the JWT token
  -d DIR, --dir DIR     Directory where the ".ssh" directory with keys can be found
  -m MAIL, --mail MAIL  E-Mail address to encode in the token
  -n CN, --cn CN        Full name to encode in the token
  -e {1d,2d,1w,2w,1m}, --exp {1d,2d,1w,2w,1m}
                        Expiration time
  -V, --version          Show version information.
  -v, --verbose          Controls the verbosity of this script
```

Another example is *dir2coll*, a utility to create a collection including all files in a local directory. If a user wants to create a new collection, it is sometimes easier to save all members as files in a directory and create the collection based on this. Types of data are inferred from the extension and a quick preview of each file by means of the module *mimetypes* of python.

```
% dir2coll -h
usage: dir2coll [-h] [-d DATA] [-u URL] [-a AUTHENTICATION] [-V] [-v VERBOSE]

optional arguments:
  -h, --help            show this help message and exit
  -d DATA, --data DATA
                        Root directory where the members of the collection are stored
  -u URL, --url URL      Base of the URL (NOT including the filename) where the files will be publicly available
  -a AUTHENTICATION, --authentication AUTHENTICATION
                        File containing the token to use during the authentication process
  -V, --version          Show version information.
  -v VERBOSE, --verbose VERBOSE
```

⁴³ Weigel, T., Almas, B., Baumgardt, F., Zastrow, T., Schwardmann, U., Hellström, M., Quinteros, J., Fleischer, D. (2017): Recommendation on Research Data Collections. - Research Data Alliance, 44p. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00022>

Controls the verbosity of this script

Also, a generic client for the service is provided. By means of this client, the user can create a collection, add members, delete and list collections and members.

```
% dcclient -h
usage: dcclient [-h] [-a AUTHENTICATION] [-V] [-v VERBOSE] {create,add,delete,list} ...

positional arguments:
  {create,add,delete,list}
                        sub-command help
  create                Command to create a collection
  add                   Command to add a member to a collection
  delete                Command to delete a collection or member
  list                  Command to list collections or members

optional arguments:
  -h, --help            show this help message and exit
  -a AUTHENTICATION, --authentication AUTHENTICATION
                        File containing the token to use during the authentication process
  -V, --version         Show version information.
  -v VERBOSE, --verbose VERBOSE
                        Controls the verbosity of this script
```

2.8.6 EOSC integration

Our aim is to make the system interoperable with other cloud and storage solutions already available within this project (e.g. F2DS) and in EOSC (e.g. Nextcloud/B2DROP).

2.9 Demonstrator #6.9 - Integrating Heterogeneous Data on Cultural Heritage

2.9.1 Objectives of the demonstrator

The main objective of this demonstrator is to avoid (or reduce) manual annotation of texts which would be required to link them with the results of scientific analyses in the same Knowledge Base. Heritage Sciences, i.e. the application of scientific experimental methods to the analysis of cultural heritage artefacts, produces a large quantity of numeric data that are only loosely related to the cultural object to which the analyses were applied. The lack of standard data models for the different technologies employed makes interoperability between datasets almost impossible. On the other hand, the same cultural objects and activities on them (studies, interventions, etc.) are documented in textual documents usually with very basic metadata. This situation requires the intervention of a human to link the documentation of scientific analyses to the documentation of the cultural object, e.g. chemical and physical analyses to a study, intended as a detailed investigation and analysis of a subject or situation (OED), by an art historian; this in the end prevents data re-use and data-driven research. The creation of a Linked Data system, as outlined above, requires the creation of a common semantic model covering both the scientific data and the content of text reports. This requires an application profile of CIDOC CRM, the standard ontology used for cultural heritage documentation, based on previous extensions such as CRM-PE, developed within the PARTHENOS⁴⁴ project, and CRM-SCI⁴⁵. Based on this newly created schema, the data encoding may be obtained by uploading the numeric results of the scientific experiments together with their metadata to create the scientific side; and then uploading the text data annotated with the same ontology. The system will then create the links between the two components of the documentation system. However, the manual annotation of texts is cumbersome and time consuming. The Use case proposes a text mining tool based on machine learning to automatically enrich the metadata of the texts by NER (Named Entity Recognition), which may then be linked to the metadata accompanying the digital outcomes of the scientific analyses, both being organized with the same ontology.

2.9.2 Targeted users

Future potential users are both heritage scientists and heritage professionals, such as conservators and restorers. The same system may be used, with little adaptation, for other research in cultural heritage.

2.9.3 Necessary data sources & services used

Data include:

- Text documentation of work on heritage artefacts, such as conservation and restoration reports;
- Results of scientific analyses on heritage artefacts.

The β -version has been run on a sample set of both placed in the INFN cloud. At present, there exist no large-scale digital repository for either. There are unresolved issues, as the lack of an overarching organization at EU level to manage and coordinate the creation of such repositories, which hamper the progress in this direction. To avoid addressing IPR issues concerning the test data, they are not publicly accessible.

⁴⁴ <https://www.parthenos-project.eu/>

⁴⁵ <https://cidoc-crm.org/crmsci/>

2.9.4 Summary of provided services

The service enables encoding text documents according to the ontology defined. It is necessary to train the NER in advance with a set of encoded documents. The tests used about a hundred training documents with satisfactory results on not encoded ones. The system should be language-independent although it has been tested on Italian texts only so far. Such encoded documents are then available for being linked to analyses results, loaded in the same system.

Figure 51: NER tool interface with annotated text

2.9.5 Guidelines to use the services

The data upload in the system is (or should be) external to the service, thus it is assumed that both scientific data, the outcomes of analyses, and the text documentation (not yet encoded) are already available to the user, possibly in a large-scale cloud-based system for storing heritage data, not yet existing. For the tests, a simple interface was created to manage such preliminary operations and create the conditions to apply the service within the INFN cloud.

The NER service itself is activated just starting it, simply selecting the set of documents to be analysed and encoded by the service. The encoded documents are then stored in a separate repository, which may duplicate or replace the original one if desired, and are available for linking to the scientific data. A short video⁴⁶ summarizing the challenges and work done in this Task is available.

2.9.6 EOSC integration

The service is ready for scaling up and being offered in the EOSC portfolio. As already mentioned, to be effective it requires the deposit of heritage data in a global FAIR repository system, centralized or federated, a feasible operation but not yet addressed at EU level. Legacy data repositories would require a conversion to the same ontology as the one used by the service, a relatively simple task using well-tested tools for the job. This has been addressed and resolved for archaeological research data, managing about two million document datasets; but in this case the data for scientific analyses are lacking. Nevertheless, the NER service was tested on a sample document set and proved to work well.

Legacy data repositories would require a conversion to the same ontology as the one used by the service, a relatively simple task using mapping tools such as those provided by the X3ML tool suite⁴⁷, implemented within the ARIADNEplus project⁴⁸. This has been addressed and resolved for archaeological research data in the above mentioned ARIADNEplus project, managing about two

⁴⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0NBHT2f5Vqk>

⁴⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/4916262#.YNrtIRmzZQI>

⁴⁸ <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

million document datasets; but in this case the data for scientific analyses are lacking. Nevertheless, the NER service was tested on a sample document set and proved to work well. To expand the field of application of the tools, more heritage science data need to be made available by the research community in this domain.

3. Conclusions

This deliverable documents the implementation of activities within every WP6 Task as well as the technical development of the Use cases (UC) at M30 of the EOsc-Pillar project. Some of the demonstrators are completed and fully operational, others need some further developments in the upcoming months until M36, as it has been stated in the second amendment to the project. The demonstrators were built with the involvement of research communities and their approach can be generalized to be applied to other scientific domains. Normally the WP6 demonstrators will be tested against targeted users of research communities at large in the final slot of the WP6 action plan. The results of this phase of testing will be presented in a following deliverable as well as an updated version of the demonstrators.